

Revolutionizing Industries: Energy Systems for Decarbonization through Geothermal Integration in Industrial Processes

System Integration and Dynamic Simulation within the GeoS-TECHIS Project

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INTRODUCTION

More than 60 % of the energy used in European industry is required for process heat, which remains largely fossil-based. Decarbonising industrial heat is therefore a key challenge for achieving climate neutrality.

Thermal energy storage (TES) enables the **decoupling of heat generation and consumption**, improving the utilisation of renewable and industrial waste heat sources. Within the **GeoS-TECHIS project**, an integrated system combining solar thermal energy, industrial waste heat recovery and TES is investigated to support the decarbonisation of SME process heat.

GEOS-TECHIS SYSTEM CONCEPT

The GeoS-TECHIS system integrates **solar thermal energy from a parabolic trough collector field** with **industrial waste heat (60 °C)** and a central **stratified hot-water TES tank**.

Heat from both sources is transferred through heat exchangers to the storage tank operating under atmospheric conditions with temperatures up to **98 °C**. The TES supplies heat to an industrial consumer with a **three-shift load profile**, thereby **decoupling heat generation from demand** and improving renewable heat utilisation.

Figure 1: Conceptual schematic of the integrated GeoS-TECHIS industrial energy system with thermal energy storage.

SYSTEM INTEGRATION STRATEGY

- Integration of **solar thermal energy and industrial waste heat**
- **Thermal cascading** between different temperature levels
- **Flexible temperature-based control strategy**
- **Scalable TES capacity** suitable for SMEs
- **Modular system architecture** enabling replication

TRNSYS MODELLING APPROACH

A dynamic system model of the integrated industrial heat supply system was developed using **TRNSYS**.

The model represents the interaction between **solar thermal collectors, industrial waste heat recovery and the stratified TES tank**, including charging and discharging processes as well as auxiliary heater operation.

The simulation framework enables the evaluation of **system flexibility, renewable heat utilisation and auxiliary energy demand** under representative SME operating conditions.

Figure 2: Simplified TRNSYS model layout of the integrated heat supply system with solar collectors, industrial waste heat, and thermal energy storage.

KEY INNOVATION

Integrated renewable and waste heat storage for SME industrial decarbonization

- **Hybrid heat sources: solar + waste heat**
- **Temperature cascading**
- **Stratified TES up to 98 °C**
- **SME-ready scalability**

SIMULATION SETUP

Reference system parameters:

- TES volume: 200 m³
- Maximum storage temperature: 98 °C
- Industrial waste heat: 60 °C

- Industrial demand profile: three-shift operation
- Heat sources: parabolic trough collectors + waste heat recovery

Boundary conditions are based on representative weather data and industrial load profiles.

RESULTS

Dynamic simulations demonstrate stable operation of the integrated system under representative SME operating conditions. The TES system buffers fluctuations between renewable heat supply and industrial demand while maintaining stable temperature stratification.

TES Temperature Behaviour

The weekly temperature profile shows stable cyclic operation without long-term drift. Charging occurs during periods of renewable heat availability, while discharging follows the industrial load.

Figure 3: Weekly evolution of the average TES temperature under representative industrial operation.

Auxiliary Heater Performance

The auxiliary heater covers residual demand not supplied by renewable heat sources and stored energy. Increasing storage capacity and collector area reduces auxiliary electricity consumption.

Figure 4: Annual auxiliary heater electricity consumption as a function of collector surface area and storage tank volume.

CONCLUSIONS & SYSTEM IMPACT

- **TES enables flexible integration of renewable and waste heat**
- **Reduced auxiliary energy demand and improved system flexibility**
- **Scalable concept for SME industrial heat supply (≤ 100 °C)**